

Title: ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND THE REVOLUTION OF WORK

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INTRODUCTION:

AI and the automation of work will change not only tasks but the way in which we structure ourselves inside of companies organizationally and in a broader sense economically and as a society.

AIM:

To prepare decision makers with the mental framework to size AI investments and be scope the change that is coming strategically to large organizations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A prospective study was conducted in of over 200 VP and above executives at fortune 500 companies with revenues over 1B USD in the USA and EU on their reediness and views on AI.

RESULTS:

Though almost all organizations are expecting disruption from the coming of automation into the workforce, most are hesitant and lack a clear vision and understanding of the technology and the wider implications to their organization.

CONCLUSIONS:

Understanding the risk, reward, and potential operating models for automation will determine the next round of winners and losers in economic completion.

KEYWORDS:

AI, automation, RPA, investment, operations, Strategy

BIOGRAPHY:

Michael is leader in Artificial Intelligence development and strategy for Fortune 500 companies. He is a dedicated member of the national strategy division within North Highland.

Michael has led multiple international cross-cultural teams in high pressure and competitive environments in France, Russia, Canada and the USA. He has managed 140+ million USD of risk exposure.

Michael has a comprehensive understanding of psychological principles with an academic background in both Business Administration and Cognitive Psychology. He is both a Canadian and Swiss citizen with an American green card.